

Ge Hong 葛洪 and Outer Alchemy 外丹

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Ge Hong 葛洪 (283-343/364), courtesy name Zhichuan 稚川, sometimes known by his sobriquet Baopuzi 抱朴子 (the Master who Embraces Simplicity), was a scholar who lived during the Eastern Jin Dynasty (317-420). Considered a prodigious writer, many texts both extant and lost are attributed to him. Amongst these, a number are concerned with matters pertaining to the extrahuman and the supernatural such as the eponymous Baopuzi 抱朴子, the hagiographic Shenxian zhuan 神仙傳 and the pharmacological Zhouhou beiji fang 肘後備急方. The importance of these texts as references for later scholars has meant Ge Hong has been cast as a figure somewhat obsessed with these matters, despite having written on a wide variety of other subjects, and that numerous scholars of the Eastern Jin were equally curious about the boundaries and margins of the human world. The Baopuzi, in particular, has often been quoted by scholars of later times in discussions of the supernatural, particularly when concerned with the practices of crafting elixirs of immortality, transmutation and other alchemical products made from a variety of materials. In the 10th C, these practices and traditions, many of which stretch back even further than the Baopuzi into high antiquity would be collectively termed 'Outer Alchemy' waidan 外丹, which was contrasted to the concept of Inner Alchemy neidan 內丹. The Baopuzi contains two chapters often identified with the study of Outer Alchemy, the Jindan 金丹 and the Huangbai 黃白, which show outer alchemy's deep concern with the development of potions, unguents and other preparations from a variety of substances, mostly what would today be identified as minerals in the Jindan with the Huangbai concerning itself with metals. Both sections explain not only the qualities of these materials, in relation to cosmological and metaphysical contexts common at the time, such as the Five Phases 五行 and Yin-Yang duality 陰陽, but also show a number of formulae to manufacture mostly elixirs of immortality, though potions to provide abilities such as invulnerability or great strength are also listed. This knowledge speaks to many of the earlier traditions of alchemical practice that existed both before and during Ge Hong's time, and Ge Hong's concerted attempts to organise and understand how these products worked and could be manufactured. Further, this Outer Alchemy provides a trove of knowledge pertaining to early chemical, mineral and metallurgical knowledge in early China.

Date Range: 283 CE - 364 CE

Region: Eastern Jin - 382 CE

Region tags: East Asia, Asia

From Tan Qixiang's "A Historical Atlas of China"

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Campany, Robert Ford (2002). *To Live As Long As Heaven and Earth: Ge Hong's Traditions of Divine Transcendents*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Source 2: Pregadio, Fabrizio (2006). *Great Clarity: Daoism and Alchemy in Early Medieval China*. Stanford

University Press.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/baopuzi>

– Source 1 Description: This is a digital edition of the Baopuzi.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Outer Alchemy is strongly associated with Daoism, particularly because of the intersection of its aim to create elixirs of immortality and Daoist beliefs and practices. Outer Alchemy itself is not 'Daoist' as it refers to a set of practices which can be engaged in by any practitioner, and Ge Hong, though strongly associated with Daoism today, would not have identified as a Daoist.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: As Outer Alchemy refers to a set of practices that could be engaged in by anyone, it is often discussed and employed by people with a wide range of religious attitudes and ideas. Ge Hong himself, for instance, was not a member of any confessionalistic religious community and debated and engaged with ideas from a variety of communities such as what would today be identified as Confucianism and Daoism. As such, although outer alchemy may share ideological perspectives with other religious groups, these are fluid, dynamic and syncretic.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: As Outer Alchemy is not confessional, it is unclear how many people would have practiced it either during Ge Hong's time or in later generations. The quest for immortality is a recurring theme in not only Chinese, but global culture, and as such it is probable that many elites during the Eastern Jin and later would have engaged with its practices in some way.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– I don't know

Notes: Practitioners of Outer Alchemy do not constitute a coherent or clear group of people. Rather the practices and traditions associated with Outer Alchemy were engaged with by choice by many different people at different times, particularly from the cultural elite, in either individual pursuits of immortality or out of intellectual curiosity.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are no leaders in Outer Alchemy, however important figures are often referenced such as Ge Hong who is identified as an early scholar engaged with the practice and Lǚ Dongbin 呂洞賓 a legendary person of the Tang said to have gained immortality himself.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: There are a variety of texts that discuss Outer Alchemy and its practices, although none are considered 'scripture'. Practices concerned with creating compounds from various minerals and metals in order to create elixirs were termed Outer Alchemy in the 11th C, and scholars from that time would compile the texts and records available to them to explain what was known about these practices. Many would identify the Cantong qi 參同契, attributed to the 2nd C figure Wei Boyang 魏伯陽, and Ge Hong's Baopuzi as the earliest and most comprehensive works on the subject, often informing later scholars in their engagement with Outer Alchemy.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Outer Alchemy itself has no 'sacred spaces'. However in the larger discussions pertaining to immortality that exist across Chinese texts, ancient mythical locales concerned with immortality do sometimes find mention or allusion in texts associated with Outer Alchemy - notably the mountain Kunlun 崑崙 where some myths depict divine peaches that bestow immortality growing, and the Queen Mother of the West 西王母, an extrahuman being who also bestows immortality, sometimes with aforementioned peaches, dwelling, and the mythical island mount Penglai 蓬萊, sometimes depicted as an archipelago with two other islands Fangzhang 方丈 and Yingzhou 瀛洲, where immortal beings and other extrahuman creatures are meant to dwell.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The mechanism by how an individual becomes immortal is not well understood and thus is subject to a great deal of discussion amongst scholars who practice Outer Alchemy. Some texts do assert that components of the body, which may be akin to a 'spirit' do endure whilst the body is cast aside, but others such as Ge Hong's Baopuzi often assert that consumption of the elixirs made lead to a creation of a new, immortal body, a process which is considered one of a number of types of 'shijie' 屍解.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Although descriptions of the afterlife are not strongly articulated in Ge Hong's texts, a variety of afterlife beliefs would have existed during his time and Outer Alchemy often asserts its goal is to 'bypass' the individual joining the afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: The Baopuzi often asserts that the elixirs of immortality consumed will see an individual create an emerge in a new immortal body, what is considered one of the types of 'shijie' 屍解. Although not necessarily comparable to systems of reincarnation such as those found in Buddhist communities, this new form can be thought of as a possible rebirth an in some later Outer Alchemy texts, this concepts are conflated or asserted.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Most practices of Outer Alchemy are concerned with manufacturing materials that will bestow immortality on an individual, as detailed in Ge Hong's Baopuzi. Upon consuming these, individuals are meant to gain eternal or a greatly extended life and are hence referred to as either xian 仙 or shenren 神人, and thus exist on the boundary of the human and the divine. Beyond an eternal or greatly extended life, what these human-divine beings are exactly is not well explained, and differences of opinion and depiction do exist in later texts. Some texts do assert that other abilities, and indeed the Baopuzi does describe making elixirs to gain preternatural abilities, are also gained upon being an immortal, but these are inconsistent and are clearly not widely shared beliefs. Textual depiction of these xian or shenren do also suggest that other abilities, particularly concerned with knowledge and awareness are present, with some possessing clairvoyant abilities, etc., but it is unclear if this is assumed to be something shared by all xian or just some individuals who have these abilities.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ge Hong discusses supernatural beings in a variety of capacities in a number of his texts, notably the *Shenxian zhuan* 神仙傳. In his discussion of what later is identified as Outer Alchemy, supernatural beings are not pertinent to the manufacture of the compounds that create immortality, although there are tales in other texts where supernatural beings teach mortals how to manufacture these or provide valuable materials to do so. The quest for immortality does suppose that the human can transcend into a supernatural being.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The traditions and practices of Outer Alchemy are concerned with the material quest for immortality. The practices associated with Inner Alchemy include discussions of virtues and other qualities which could be understood as moral. Owing to their relationship, it is not uncommon to see some mentions of these in outer alchemy, but they are not consistent nor required for the practices.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Although celibacy is not a concern of Outer Alchemy, some texts concerned with Inner Alchemy do argue that celibacy will help achieve immortality or lengthen one's lifespan. Owing to the strong interaction between both Inner and Outer Alchemy, it is possible to encounter such prescriptions in Outer Alchemical texts.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Although fasting is not a concern of Outer Alchemy, some texts concerned with Inner Alchemy do argue for fasting and other dietary restrictions to help achieve immortality. Owing to the strong interaction between both Inner and Outer Alchemy, it is possible to encounter such prescriptions in Outer Alchemical texts. Ge Hong's Baopuzi, for instance, does discuss certain foods and diets and their benefits on the body, although this is found in other sections of the text not concerned with Outer Alchemy.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There were well established pedagogies and formal and informal education institutions during Ge Hong's time particularly associated with the Imperial system. Further, Buddhist communities were growing at this time and bringing additional education opportunities to the region. However, for the most part education, both formal and informal, remained the purview of the elite.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: Formal education institutions during Ge Hong's time would only take male pupils. However, as education was often family based, particularly amongst the elite, it was not uncommon for females to be educated alongside their male siblings. There were also other informal education routes available to females in elite social classes.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Most people who would participate in practices identified as Outer Alchemy during the Jin would either be or have interacted with formal bureaucracy if not participated in it, as Ge Hong did. This is due to the strong reliance on elite culture that the Jin Imperial structures engaged in as well as the intersection of education with elite culture.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Most institutional bureaucracies during the Jin were centralised and imperially controlled, however growing Buddhist monastic institutions, local court structures and other polities also existed which some participants in Outer Alchemy may have frequented as well.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Outer Alchemical practices were written in Classical Chinese which was the standard lingua franca in premodern East Asia. There are traditions in Daoism of using special scripts particularly for talismans, fulu 符籙, and Buddhist texts would also often use Sanskrit and Pali, however whereas some practitioners may have been familiar with these and used them for certain purposes, they would not be employed to transmit information pertaining to Outer Alchemy.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: As practitioners of Outer Alchemy would have participated in a number of different communities, including religious ones, the calendars they used would have been dictated by those communities. Individuals such as Ge Hong would have most likely been familiar with the imperial calendar that the Jin empire employed. Ge Hong does place stock in and discuss how the supernatural is affected by time, highlighting beliefs in taboo days and discussing auspicious omens connected to the calendar. Although this does not seem to impact the study of Outer Alchemy, related activities such as when to rest or avoid certain activities may have some incidental impact.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Imperial calendar modeled on the conventions established in the Han (206 BCE- 220 CE) was in wide use during the Jin.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No